

STUDIES ON 'LIPASE' FROM OIL SEEDS. PART VI. HYDROLYSIS OF SOME ALIPHATIC ESTERS BY RICINUS LIPASE

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Hydrolysis of some esters of butyric and propionic acids was carried out using acetone-dried lipase in order to study the effect of change of the number of carbon atoms in the alcohol on the hydrolysis of esters by lipase.

The hydrolysis of some aliphatic esters was carried out using acetone-dried lipase in order to study the effect of the number of carbon atoms in the alcohol and acid on the hydrolysis of esters. So the hydrolysis of methyl, ethyl, *n*- and isopropyl, *n*- and isobutyl, *n*- amyl esters of propionic and butyric acids was carried out.

E X P E R I M E N T A L

In each flask 0.018 g. mol. of ester solution, 1 g. of lipase and 10 c.c. of ether solvent and a few drops of toluene were taken and incubated at 37°. At different intervals of time, 1 c.c. portion of it was taken, neutral alcohol (25 c.c.) added, warmed for some time and titrated against *N*/10 sodium hydroxide. The initial reading was also taken before starting the experiment. From the difference in readings, the percentage hydrolysis was calculated. The results are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

Esters.	Percentage hydrolysis on days.					
	1 st.	2 nd.	3 rd.	4 th.	5 th.	6 th.
Methyl propionate	40.1	44.8	49.2	50.8	48.5	—
Ethyl "	45.0	48.5	50.7	51.9	51.5	—
<i>n</i> -Propyl "	37.0	39.2	42.5	46.7	45.8	—
<i>iso</i> Propyl "	17.2	19.1	24.8	31.6	35.8	34.5
<i>n</i> -Butyl "	20.4	24.7	31.2	34.5	33.6	—
<i>iso</i> Butyl "	21.6	25.0	32.6	33.9	32.5	—
<i>n</i> -Amyl "	14.9	25.8	33.7	32.5	—	—
Methyl butyrate	44.0	46.0	51.5	50.5	—	—
Ethyl "	45.5	51.5	43.5	—	—	—
<i>n</i> -Propyl "	38.2	40.9	43.7	45.9	43.7	—
<i>iso</i> Propyl "	15.5	18.8	22.6	39.2	36.7	34.8
<i>n</i> -Butyl "	21.2	23.8	30.9	33.7	32.3	—
<i>iso</i> Butyl "	22.6	25.8	33.4	33.7	31.8	—
<i>n</i> -Amyl "	19.8	28.1	29.2	31.2	30.5	—

From the above table, it is found that the percentage hydrolysis goes on decreasing from methyl to amyl butyrate and methyl to amyl propionate, and so it can be inferred that the increase in the number of carbon atoms in the alcohol decreases the percentage hydrolysis from methyl to amyl ester. In other words, the hydrolysis is difficult in case of higher esters.

The percentage hydrolysis is always greater in case of the *normal* ester than the *iso* one. In the case of *n*- and *isopropyl* esters, the difference in percentage hydrolysis may be due to difference in structure [*n*-propyl ester is $\text{CH}_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{COOC}_3\text{H}_7$, and *isopropyl* ester is $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{CH}\cdot\text{COOC}_3\text{H}_7$], whereas in the case of *n*- and *isobutyl* esters, the difference in percentage may be due to the difference in densities (density of *n*-butyl ester is 0.872 and the density of *isobutyl* ester is 0.861) as their structures are the same.

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